

PROBABILISTIC MULTI-HYPOTHESIS TRACKING IN A MULTI-SENSOR, MULTI-TARGET ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the Probabilistic Multi-Hypothesis Tracking (PMHT) Algorithm, a data fusion algorithm recently developed by Streit and Luginbuhl [1, 2], is extended to handle multiple sensors. In addition, performance of multi-target tracking algorithms is discussed in terms of the Cramer-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) criterion that is computed from the marginalized measurement PMHT log-likelihood function. Simulation results for one set of scenarios are presented and an initialization procedure for the bearings only measurement case is recommended.

1. INTRODUCTION

In its original formulation [1, 2], PMHT addresses the problem of origin uncertainty in multi-target tracking when multiple measurements are received without target labels, that is, the target of origin of a measurement is unknown. Unlike traditional methods that assign a single measurement to a single target model, it introduces the new and somewhat unconventional concept that every measurement is assigned to every target model. PMHT is derived by formulating a joint measurement-assignment density, where the measurement-to-track assignments are modeled by a discrete but unknown random variable. The joint density is marginalized over the assignments, and the Expectation-Maximization (EM) method is used to estimate a set of measurement-to-track probabilities for each measurement and each target model. These soft measurement-to-track probabilities are used to create a 'synthetic' measurement for each target model, where a synthetic measurement is a probabilistically weighted combination of all the observed measurements. The PMHT algorithm decouples the estimation problem into N (number of target models) independent target

estimation problems because the synthetic measurement assignments are known. The procedure iterates between soft assignment estimation, synthetic measurement computation and target state estimation to converge to a solution. The solution (at the M-Step of the EM process) is shown to be the standard least squares solution for a single target if no process noise is included in the target model, and to the standard Kalman Filter solution for a single target, if process noise is included in the target model.

The basic PMHT approach is extended in this paper to handle multiple non-collocated sensors. In this particular derivation the sensors are assumed to observe identical surveillance regions. The case in which the sensors are assumed to have non-identical overlapping observation regions is not addressed here, but PMHT can easily be extended to this case in a straightforward manner. It is shown that measurement-to-target probabilities can be computed as before for all measurement-to-target model combinations, and that synthetic measurements for each target model and sensor combination are obtained by combining only measurements within each sensor. The solution with the new synthetic measurements for each target model is identical to standard techniques that treat the assignments as known. Both linear and non-linear situations are easily handled. The Multi-Sensor PMHT (MSPMHT) algorithm is computationally practical because it avoids enumeration over time of measurement-to-track assignments. The linear multi-sensor case with collocated sensors and similar linear measurements, which results in a form identical to the single sensor PMHT, was also considered in [3]. The original PMHT algorithm [1, 2] is inherently multi-sensor if the defining models and parameters are appropriately re-interpreted [4].

The performance of the MSPMHT algorithm is presented for one set of scenarios. The practical case of bearings only observations from two sensors is used to

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demonstrate the theory, present results and recommend an initialization procedure. Performance is evaluated by comparing the simulation results to the CRLB derived from the PMHT marginalized measurement density, as well to the CRLB of the single target case (e.g. known assignments). The CRLB does not seem to have a closed-form solution, so numerical results are shown for the sample scenarios.

2. MSPMHT DERIVATION

The MSPMHT algorithm derivation is outlined in the context of the multi-target tracking problem, with the assumption that there is no process noise in the target model. This assumption is not limiting and with minor modifications all results are applicable to the case where process noise is included.

Let there be M targets each of which moves according to the standard discrete time linear model:

$$X_m(t+1) = F_m(t)X_m(t) + G_m(t)u_m(t) \quad (1)$$

for $t = 1, \dots, T$. In (1) the subscript m is used to represent the trajectory of the m^{th} target. The matrices $F_m(t)$ and $G_m(t)$ are assumed to be known. The measurements are observed at each sensor based on the following standard observation model

$$z_{r_t^s} = H^s(X_m, t) + w_{r_t^s} \quad (2)$$

The observation function H^s is also assumed to be known and can be different for each sensor. The added observation random sequence $w_{r_t^s}$, is assumed to be zero mean, white and Gaussian. Let the $Z = \{z_{r_t^s}\}$ be the set of all observed measurements, and let $K = \{k_{r_t^s}\}$ be a set of discrete random variables which are used to indicate an assignment for the r^{th} measurement with $r_t^s = 1, \dots, n_t^s$ from the s^{th} sensor with $s = 1, \dots, S$, at time t , $t = 1, \dots, T$. The random variable $k_{r_t^s}$ can take values in the range $1, \dots, M$. Assume that measurements between time scans, within each time scan, and between sensors are independent, as is the assignment of measurements to target model. Let $X = \{X_m\}$, $m = 1, \dots, M$ be the parameter set for all the targets where $X_m = [x_{0m}, y_{0m}, v_{xm}, v_{ym}]^T$ represents the target initial position and velocity for the m^{th} target. Under the independence conditions the joint density of the measurements and assignments parameterized by X is given by

$$P(Z, K; X) = \prod_{s=1}^S \prod_{t=1}^T \prod_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} \pi_{r_t^s}^{m} N(z_{r_t^s}; H^s(X_{k_{r_t^s}=m}, t)), \quad (3)$$

where $\pi_{r_t^s}^m$ is the notation used to indicate the *a priori* probability $P(k_{r_t^s} = m)$. The notation $k_{r_t^s} = m$ is used simply to denote that the r^{th} measurement from the s^{th} sensor at time step t is assigned to the m^{th} target model. The marginal density $P(Z; X)$ can now be computed by summing equation (3) over the discrete random variable K .

$$P(Z; X) = \prod_{s=1}^S \prod_{t=1}^T \prod_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} \sum_{m=1}^M \pi_{r_t^s}^m N(z_{r_t^s}; H^s(X_m, t)) \quad (4)$$

The conditional density is now easily obtained:

$$P(K|Z; X) = \prod_{s=1}^S \prod_{t=1}^T \prod_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} w_{k_{r_t^s}, m} \quad (5)$$

The weights are equivalent to the single sensor PMHT and represent the measurement to target probabilities and are given by

$$w_{k_{r_t^s}, m} = \frac{\pi_{r_t^s}^m N(z_{k_{r_t^s}}(t); H^s(X_m, t))}{\sum_{p=1}^M \pi_{r_t^s}^p N(z_{k_{r_t^s}}(t); H^s(X_p, t))} \quad (6)$$

By using (3), (4) and (5) we now obtain the Q function in the E step of the E-M algorithm

$$\begin{aligned} Q(X^{n+1}; X^n) &= \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} \sum_{m=1}^M (\log \pi_{r_t^s}^m) w_{r_t^s, m}^n \\ &+ \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} \sum_{m=1}^M (\log N(z_{r_t^s}; H^s(X_m^{n+1}, t))) w_{r_t^s, m}^n \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) is in the same form as the single sensor PMHT with the additional sum over the sensors. For the M-step of the EM process we proceed to take the gradient of the Q function with respect to X^{n+1} . This is easily shown to decouple into the estimation of M targets with pseudo-measurements formed for each target by combining all the measurements based on the computed weights on each individual sensor. See [1, 2] for further discussion. The pseudo-measurements for each target model are formed by

$$\tilde{z}_{t, m}^s = \frac{\sum_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} (w_{r_t^s, m}^{n+1}) z_{r_t^s}}{\sum_{r_t^s=1}^{n_t^s} w_{r_t^s, m}^{n+1}} \quad (8)$$

It is important to note that pseudo-measurements are formed by combining measurements obtained with each sensor. This easily allows for the combination of multiple sensors with different observation spaces (i.e. active and passive).

MSPMHT can now be stated in algorithmic form:

1. Determine the initial values of the parameter set X . This is the initialization step and is critical to successful algorithm performance.
2. Calculate the weights for each sensor for all measurement to target model combinations at each time step.
3. Calculate the synthetic measurement, $\tilde{z}_{t,m}^s$ for each target model and each sensor.
4. For each target model apply the appropriate estimation algorithm (in our example the Levenberg–Marquardt nonlinear regression procedure is used).
5. Repeat steps 1-4 until convergence is reached.

3. THE MSPMHT CRLB

The marginal MSPMHT density in (4) is used to compute the CRLB. In a strict sense it is not the true CRLB since this marginal density is specific to the MSPMHT algorithm and might not be the best one. However, we propose using it to derive a bound for the multi-target case and to compare its value to that of the single target CRLB under the assumption that the measurement assignments are known. Let $g(z_{r_t^s}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \pi_{r_t^s}^m N(z_{r_t^s}; H^s(X_m, t))$ be used to denote the Gaussian sum density. To compute the CRLB we proceed by computing the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) in the form given by

$$I[X]_{ij} = -E_Z \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log P(Z; X)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right] \quad (9)$$

where $P(Z; X)$ is given by equation (4). In (9) the FIM is an $M \times M$ matrix of partials with x_i, x_j in the parameter list X . We proceed to compute the partial derivatives $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}$ of the marginal density in (4), which are needed for the FIM.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \log(P(Z; X)) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{r=1}^{n_t} \log g(z_{r_t^s}) \\ &= \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{r=1}^{n_t} \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} g(z_{r_t^s})}{g(z_{r_t^s})} \right] \\ &- \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{r=1}^{n_t} \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} g(z_{r_t^s}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} g(z_{r_t^s})}{g^2(z_{r_t^s})} \right] \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

By substituting (10) into (9) and simplifying we obtain the final form of the FIM matrix

$$[I(X)]_{ij} = \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T n_t^s \int_z \left(\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} g(z_{r_t^s}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} g(z_{r_t^s})}{g(z_{r_t^s})} \right) dz \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) does not seem to have a closed form solution. In this paper numerical computation of the FIM was done for the scenarios that we used and the results were compared to that of the single target CRLB in which case the assignments were known. Results for one scenario family are shown in section 4.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

4.1. Scenario Description

The MSPMHT algorithm is tested with a family of seven scenarios with similar geometry. The overall geometry for the set is shown in Figure 1. Two stationary passive sensors (not shown) positioned at location (0, 0) and (0, -1000) meters respectively, are observing bearing measurements from two targets with linear motion in the X-Y plane. Target 1 starts at (5000, 5000) with velocity (0, 14) in meters/second. Target 2 executes a parallel course with the same velocity, but different initial position as indicated by the circles in Figure 1. The relative bearing differences between the targets are shown in Figure 2. The normalized mean bearing difference between the two targets is indicated in the bearing lines of Figure 2.

For each scenario a set of 50 measurements for each target and sensor ($S = 2, T = 50, n_t^s = 2$) is generated with a sampling interval of 30 seconds. The additive bearing noise is assumed to be white Gaussian with $\sigma = 1^\circ$. A sample set of measurements from sensor 1 for the scenario with mean bearing difference of 3.3° is shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, the measurements from target 1 and 2 are mixed more than half the time. The problem is further compounded by the fact that measurements from the second sensor are also near, even though they are not shown in Figure 3. The MSPMHT solution, the MLE solution, as well as the target track and initial target estimates are shown in Figure 4. The MLE solution with known measurement to target assignments is included to indicate that PMHT is very close to the optimum for this particular data set. An important element of the MSPMHT algorithm is the computation of the weights. These weights are basic to the algorithm since they are used to assign the measurements to a target. The final weights for the sample scenario are shown in Figure 5. For the first 500 seconds one of the weights tends to be close to one, which means that a particular measurement is favored for this target, while the other one is used very little. Between 500 and 1500 seconds the weights tend to be mixed, with varying assignment. This is expected since the target measurements are not statistically

separable at this time period. To compare MSPMHT performance to the numerical (MSPMHT) CRLB and to the standard Single Target CRLB, 100 trials were run for each of the scenarios shown in Figures 1 and 2. Discussion of those results follows.

4.2. Initialization

The most challenging problem that we addressed in evaluating the MSPMHT algorithm was that of initialization. In our first attempt we utilized the first two measured bearings from sensor 1 and default range and velocity parameters for each target at (10000, 20000) meters and (10, 10) meters/second respectively. This method was unsuccessful because the pseudo measurements of MSPMHT lead to a false global maximum. The answer for this problem lies in the MSPMHT weights and is discussed further in the following section. To overcome this problem we utilized a process of measurement variance deflation similar to that proposed in [5]. The measurement variance inside the E-step of the MSPMHT algorithm was increased in the early steps to allow all measurements to be considered as a solution for each target track. The variance was deflated with factors {20, 10, 7, 5, 2} for the first five steps of the EM process. The remaining steps were then executed with the correct measurement variance until convergence. This procedure was fixed for all trials. Initialization is probably the most difficult problem in implementing PMHT and must be considered carefully.

4.3. Results

The results from all the scenarios for target 2 are presented in Figure 6. Target 1 has similar trends and is not shown here. For details see [6]. Two sets of curves are presented for each of the 4 parameters [x_{01} , y_{01} , vx_1 , vy_1]. The first set (solid) represents the ratio of σ values between the numerically computed bound and single target CRLB with known assignments. The second set of curves (dashed) represents the ratio of the σ computed from the simulations relative to the σ of the single target CRLB. Ideally four dimensional ellipsoids from the CRLB should have been used, but representation is a problem and we chose the square root of the diagonal of the covariance matrix as a representative figure of merit. To summarize the results some data selection is performed. First, a decision is made on which PMHT solution is associated with each target, since the MSPMHT algorithm does not identify which of the solutions belongs to each target. The set of estimated to true parameters with least error is used. Second, outliers are removed from

the data. Several of the MSPMHT estimates are erroneous. We believe this to be a result of the initialization process. A threshold of $\pm 5\sigma$ of each estimate is used to exclude the data. If any of the parameters in X_1 and X_2 lie beyond this range the entire solution is excluded. This results in excluding {0, 0, 12, 19, 4, 5, 3} data points out of 100 trials for mean bearing separations of {0.6, 1.1, 1.5, 1.9, 2.6, 3.3, 5.6} respectively.

4.4. Discussion

Figure 6 is discussed in two parts. The first and most practical of the two parts are the results with mean bearing difference greater than 2° (greater than 2σ). The theoretical and simulation results seem to agree in all but one (vx_1) of the parameters. MSPMHT correctly estimates the parameters within approximately 25% of the known assignment case. Theoretical and simulation results disagree for mean bearing difference of less than 2° . It seems that MSPMHT estimates better than the single target bound. When targets are so close that their measurements are statistically indistinguishable, MSPMHT merges the targets and the MSPMHT weights¹ tend to converge to a value of 1/2. This was confirmed by observing the final MSPMHT weights, which converged to 1/2 for these cases. MSPMHT solutions for targets close together are not identifiable (in a strict statistical sense) because interchanging the target labels does not change the likelihood structure.

Figure 5 can be used to illustrate this point. When the measurements tend to be far apart, MSPMHT weights converge to unity for one of the measurement-to-target combinations, which in essence assigns that measurement to one of the targets. When the measurement separation is not statistically significant, the weights are approximately equal from each measurement to each target. The single merged target has twice the measurements of a single target alone and the variance of the estimate is reduced proportionally. In this case the MSPMHT model is mismatched with the data and the target solutions are not distinguishable. Overall, based on the scenario presented, the results shown in Figure 6 indicate that MSPMHT seems to be a good estimation algorithm when the assignments are unknown. In all but one (vx_1) of the parameters theoretical and experimental results for the limited trials performed agree for bearing separations of 2° to 6° .

¹When values for the weights are given they are approximate

5. SUMMARY

A multi-sensor extension to the original PMHT algorithm was presented. The derivation was outlined and performance was discussed relative to the single target CRLB for a set of sample runs. Simulations were in good agreement with theoretical results for the scenarios that were tested for bearing separation of 2σ or greater. For those cases the theoretical bound based on the MSPMHT density was shown to be within approximately 25% of the single target CRLB for the test scenario. A strategy of variance deflation in the EM step of the algorithm was proposed as one solution to the difficult problem of initialization and was demonstrated for a sample set. Extension of the above concepts to include clutter and evaluation for other scenarios is recommended.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1: Scenario Geometry

Figure 2: Bearing Differences

Figure 3: Sample Measurement Set

Figure 5: Sample Weights

Figure 4: True, Initial and Final Target Estimates

Figure 6: Sigma Ratio for Target 2